

Synthesis and Pharmacology of 2,5-Disubstituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles

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A series of new 2,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles carrying 1,2-diarylethyl/aryloxyalkyl moieties at 2-position and phenyl, amino, mercapto, thioacetic acid or ethyl thioacetate groups at 5 position were synthesised and evaluated for their pharmacological activity. Some members exhibited mild to strong antiinflammatory and CNS depressant action in experimental animals.

1,3,4-Oxadiazole moiety has been investigated with a view to obtaining compounds of biological¹⁻³ and pesticidal^{4,5} interest. Our earlier work on the synthesis of 2,3-diarylpropionhydrazides⁶, as intermediates for title compounds revealed CNS stimulant, antiinflammatory and hypotensive action in experimental animals.

Incorporation of aryloxyalkyl moiety in the heterocyclic residues⁷ such as pyrroles and pyrazoles has led to the compounds possessing CNS depressant, antiinflammatory and hypotensive action. With a view to explore the possibility of obtaining biologically useful compounds, the present paper describes the synthesis of 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles represented by structures I and II, carrying 1,2-diarylethyl and aryloxyalkyl moieties.

R = C₆H₅, NH₂, SH, SCH₂COOH or
SCH₂COOC₂H₅
R₁ = H, 4-OCH₃ or 3,4-(OCH₃)₂
R₂ = H, 4-OCH₃ or 3,4-(OCH₃)₂

R = NH₂ or SH
R₁, R₃, R₄ = H or CH₃
R₂ = H or Cl

Scheme—1

The synthesis of I and II was accomplished as shown in Scheme 1. The title compounds (I and II) along with their pharmacological data are described in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—2-SUBSTITUTED-5(1',2'-DIARYLETHYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES(I)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. (°C)	LD ₅₀ mg/kg (i.p. mice)	Antiinflammatory action (%inhibition at 1/10 dose of LD ₅₀)	%Decrease in motor activity at 1/10 dose of LD ₅₀
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	124	>800	24	33
2.	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	H	101	>800	—	30
3.	C ₆ H ₅	H	4-OCH ₃	110	>800	—	21
4.	NH ₂	H	H	199	>800	14	22
5.	NH ₂	H	4-OCH ₃	178	>800	28	24
6.	NH ₂	4-OCH ₃	H	176	600	34	15
7.	NH ₂	4-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	194	—	—	—
8.	NH ₂	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	H	182	>800	31	45
9.	NH ₂	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	170-71	>800	24	35
10.	SH	H	H	75	300	34	38
11.	SH	H	4-OCH ₃	136	>800	10	19
12.	SH	4-OCH ₃	H	96	700	30	38
13.	SH	4-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	90	700	40	—
14.	SH	H	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	109	—	—	—
15.	SH	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	169-70	>800	30	48
16.	SOH ₂ COOH	H	H	118	600	33	13
17.	SOH ₂ COOC ₂ H ₅	H	H	58	>800	17	40
18.	SOH ₂ COOH	4-OCH ₃	H	134	600	26	33
19.	SOH ₂ COOC ₂ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	H	51-52	>800	28	25

TABLE 2—2-SUBSTITUTED-5(ARYLOXYALKYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES(II)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	m.p.(°C) or b.p.°C/mm	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg) (i.p. mice)	Antiinflammatory action (%inhibition at 1/10 dose of LD ₅₀)	%Decrease in motor activity at 1/10 dose of LD ₅₀	Hypotensive action at 5 mg/kg mm(min.)
20.	NH ₂	H	H	H	H	159-60	400	12	—	-40(60)
21.	NH ₂	CH ₃	H	H	H	136-37	600	9	—	-33(20)
22.	NH ₂	H	Cl	H	H	161	700	10	—	—
23.	NH ₂	CH ₃	Cl	H	H	167	>800	24	37	-40(45)
24.	NH ₂	H	H	CH ₃	H	153-54	>800	32	10	—
25.	NH ₂	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	162-63	>800	12	15	—
26.	NH ₂	H	Cl	CH ₃	H	161-62	>800	43	24	-22(40)
27.	NH ₂	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	H	165-66	>800	39	—	—
28.	NH ₂	H	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	193-94	>800	25	—	—
29.	NH ₂	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	176-78	>800	9	51	-35(10)
30.	NH ₂	H	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	205	>800	17	—	—
31.	NH ₂	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	182-83	>800	—	43	-30(5)
32.	SH	CH ₃	H	H	H	94-95	400	15	—	—
33.	SH	CH ₃	Cl	H	H	130	300	22	—	—
34.	SH	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	H	80-81	300	25	18	—
35.	SH	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	210-213/1	400	—	—	—
36.	SH	H	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	131-32	700	17	24	—
37.	SH	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	210-14/1.3	500	—	—	—

All compounds analysed correctly for C, H and N.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 221 infrared spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were taken on a Varian A60A spectrometer using TMS as the external standard.

2,3-Diarylpropionic acid hydrazides and aryloxyalkyl carboxylic acid hydrazides were prepared by the method of Conti⁶.

2-Phenyl-5(1',2'-diphenylethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole(1, Table 1) :

A mixture of 2,3-diphenylpropionic acid hydrazide (7.20 g, 0.03M) and benzoic acid (3.30 g, 0.03M)

in phosphorusoxychloride (15 ml) was refluxed for 5 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into ice water, made basic by adding sodium bicarbonate solution and the resulting solid was filtered. The dried solid was recrystallised from chloroform to give the title compound. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3015, 3040 (aromatic C-H), 2925, 2840 (alkyl C-H), 1630 (C=N) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C).

Compounds 2 and 3 were obtained in a similar manner.

2-Amino-5-[α -(3'-methyl-4'-chlorophenoxy) isopropyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole (31, Table 2) :

To an ethanolic solution (60 ml) of α -(3-methyl-4-chlorophenoxy) isobutyric acid hydrazide (12.10 g,

0.05M), cyanogen bromide (5.8 g, 0.055M) was added. The reaction mixture was warmed at 45° for 30 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralised with potassium bicarbonate solution. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from methanol.

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3290, 3120 (NH₂), 3000 (aromatic C-H), 2925, 2850 (alkyl C-H), 1640 (C=N), 1590 (aromatic C=C) and 1240 cm⁻¹ (ether linkage). PMR (CDCl₃) δ 6.52-7.2 (m, 3H, aromatic), 6.23 (b, 2H, NH₂, exchangeable with D₂O), 2.35 (s, 3H, methyl attached to aromatic ring) and 1.80 (s, 6H, isopropyl group protons).

Compounds 4-9 and 20-30 were synthesised in the same way.

2-(3'-Methyl-4'-chlorophenoxyethyl)- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazoline-5-thione (33, Table 2) :

A mixture of 3-methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (21.5 g, 0.1M), potassium hydroxide (5.61 g, 0.1M), carbon disulfide (35 ml) and ethanol (150 ml) was heated under reflux until the evolution of hydrogen sulfide ceases. The reaction mixture was concentrated, dissolved in water and acidified with HCl. The resulting product was recrystallised from methanol to give the above compounds.

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3300 (NH), 3020 (aromatic C-H), 2910, 2850 (alkyl C-H), 1630 (C=N), 1590 (aromatic C=C) and 1245 cm⁻¹ (ether linkage). PMR (CDCl₃) δ 10.0 (b, 1H, NH, exchangeable with D₂O), 6.57-7.13 (m, 3H, aromatic), 2.3 (s, 3H, methyl attached to aromatic ring).

Compounds 10-15 and 32,34,35,36, 37 were also prepared in the same way.

5-(1',2'-Diphenylethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthioacetic acid (16, Table 1) :

A solution of 2-(1',2'-diphenylethyl)- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazoline-5-thione (8.46 g, 0.03M) in DMF (15 ml) and aqueous sodium hydroxide (0.06M in 20 ml H₂O) was treated with a mixture of monochloroacetic acid (3.12 g, 0.033M) and aqueous sodium bicarbonate (0.033M in 15 ml H₂O) on a steam bath for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was subsequently diluted with water and acidified with HCl. The liberated acid was recrystallised from methanol to give the title compound. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1720 (C=O) and 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Compound 18 was prepared in a similar manner.

Ethyl [5-(1',2'-diphenylethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-ylthio] acetate (17, Table 1) :

2-(1',2'-Diphenylethyl)- Δ^2 -1,3,4-oxadiazoline-5-thione (5.64 g, 0.02M) in DMF (20 ml) was reacted with bromoethyl acetate (3.34 g, 0.12M) in presence of K₂CO₃ (7.0 g) on a steam bath for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured over ice and left overnight. The solid thus separated was recrystallised from methanol.

Compound 19 was prepared in the same way.

Pharmacological Evaluation :

The compounds listed in Tables 1 and 2 were subjected to primary screening in experimental animals. Toxicity (LD₅₀), antiinflammatory, hypotensive and motor activities were determined by literature methods⁹⁻¹¹. Compounds in the present investigation exhibited mild to moderate CNS depressant action and moderate to strong anti-inflammatory activity.

Compounds 6, 26 and 27 exhibited significant antiinflammatory activity while compound 23 showed appreciable hypotensive activity.

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